

Some Factors Affecting Geotextiles Seam Strength Using Surface Response Methodology (Case Study)

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Abstract:

In Egypt, the long coastline of north and east Egypt is deeply connected with the culture, life and traditions of the country. Beach conservation, management and development works are effected to aid tourism to a large extent. Nowadays these coasts possess a potential erosion challenge due to increasing and dwindling of sea levels because global warming and land encroachment to the beachside. This study focuses on the study of investigate how various sewing parameters affected seam strength of nonwoven geotextiles which are used in coastal protection and offshore engineering structures in Egypt. In this study, the effects of nonwoven geotextiles sewing parameters namely, sewing yarn count, number of sewing lines and stitch type are studied and have been optimized using three variables Factorial design of Response Surface Methodology except stitch type with only two levels. The seam strength of the prepared samples was determined according to EN ISO 10321 standard technique. It is determined that polyester sewing yarn count of 15x3 and 18x3 tex with 2 or 3 number of sewing lines with 401 stitch type for nonwoven geotextiles seam strength results are the best optimal responses.

Keywords: *Geotextiles, Sewing yarn count. Number of sewing line, Stitch type, Response surface methodology (RSM), Seam strength*

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1. Introduction

Geotextiles are separated into two groups: woven and nonwoven. Any synthetic or natural materials may be used to create geotextiles. Synthetic polymers including polypropylene (PP), polyester (PET), and high density polyethylene (HDPE) make up the majority of synthetic products. It is noted that these polymers have very high resistance to biological and chemical degradation. Generally, glass fibers, polyamides, and polyvinyl chloride (PVC) are used less. Natural materials include cotton, jute, sisal, flax, and other fibers; they should only be used in the short term applications because they degrade quickly [1]. The geotextiles components are continuous filaments or staple fibers joined together to form a planar textile construction. The polymeric staple fibers used to make nonwoven geotextiles are constantly extruded and cut (2 to 6 inches) long. The mass of fibers is next needle punched, heat bonded, or both procedures are used. The mechanical entanglement of the fibers with the use of a series of specialized needles is known as needle punching. Heat bonding is the technique of joining fibers with low melt together using heat and pressure at contact sites to form a nonwoven fabric [2, 3].

Nonwoven geotextile can be used in marine constructions including breakwaters, revetments, and beach protection, among others. In general, geotextile should retain soil while allowing water to flow. The high tensile strength of the geotextile is essential for other coastal applications such soil bank reinforcement [4].

Sewing is used to reduce the cost and time of overlays, while in others it needs to be done as part of the application design. A few inches of geotextile from each piece or sheet are often needed for a stitched seam, as compared to two or three meters for an overlap [5]. Geotextile woven or non-woven is able to be stitched. Seaming adjacent

geotextile fabrics also enables for rapid application of geotextile across a broad area, which is especially helpful when soil conditions are poor and/or access is limited, such as when underwater set up is necessary (6). The use of sewn seams in the strong axis direction (crosswise machine direction CMD) is accepted; however, the sewn seam strength zone is lowered to the strength of the geotextile nonwoven fabrics.

YLI Corporation provides factual information regarding sewing yarns and sewing needles appropriate for different types of materials (7). Two crucial elements influence the appropriate sewing needle selection: first, the yarn to be used and second, the fabric to be stitched. In the industry, yarn breakage brought on by a variety of factors, such as the following, can be minimized by using yarn / machine needle charts as guidance.

- Choosing an inappropriate yarn for the job.
- A damaged or the incorrect needle.
- Defects in the yarn.
- Excessive elongation.
- Having excessive tension when sewing.
- Worn machine parts.
- Unbalanced machinery.
- The operator's handling. (8)

The most popular sewing yarn materials are Kevlar, polyester, polyester, and polypropylene. When sewing stronger geotextiles with cross-machine direction strengths of 52.5 kN/m (300 lb/in) or more, polyester yarn is typically used. Geotextiles with lower tensile strengths may be seamed using polypropylene yarn. Kevlar yarn is incredibly pricey while being extremely strong. Kevlar yarn hasn't provided much help since the foundation geotextile's cross-machine direction tensile strength, which is much less in comparison to the Kevlar yarn, ultimately determines how strong the seam will be (9).

The act of interlacing sewing yarns in or around a material to create a stitch is called stitch formation. A seam is created when a stitch with a certain shape is used to arrange material layers. There are several international and national standards that categorize different stitch and seam kinds (10 - 11).

To guarantee that 100% coverage will be maintained throughout the backfilling process when there are poor subgrade conditions present, geotextile panels are often sewn in the field.

Modern field industrial sewing machines come in a variety of designs and are quite technologically sophisticated mechanically and electronically. Depending on the sort of stitch the machine makes, there are field machines that function with either one yarn or two yarns. Because of their strength and extensibility, chain stitch 101 fig. 1 and chain stitch 401 fig. 2 are frequently used. In these stitches, a single yarn for the needle interloops with itself on the back of the cloth. In chain stitch 401 fig. 2, a needle yarn interloops with a looper yarn.

Figure 1 - chain stitch 101

Figure 2 - chain stitch 401

2. Materials & Methods

The major factor in reaching the requisite seam strength is the geotextile's ultimate wide width tensile strength in the cross-machine direction, which is calculated using EN ISO 10319, "Standard Test Method for Geosynthetics — Wide-width tensile test". The use of sewn seams may be permitted in the strong axis direction; however, the strength of the geotextile will be reduced to the strength of the sewn seam. The EN ISO 10321 "Standard Test Method for Geotextiles – Tensile test for joints/Seams by wide width method" is followed for testing the seam strength on a broad specimen. Even though several potential methods for producing extremely high seam strength are now being studied, seam strengths frequently reach 90% or more of the maximum geotextiles wide width tensile strength in the cross-machine direction. The qualities of the geotextile affect the seam strength.

2.1. Geotextiles

A needle punched nonwoven geotextiles is one created from webs of fibers with certain fibers pushed upward or downward by barbed needles. This needling process interlocks fibers and uses the effects of friction to hold the structure together. A binding point is a collection of fibers having varying orientations that are held together by friction forces. The usage of hot melt adhesive fibers (low melt fibers) is one of the most convenient techniques for integrating nonwoven structures. Adhesive fibers are fibers that may form adhesive connections with other fibers due to their melting properties and special effects of hot calendar in finishing process. Nonwoven geotextiles, utilized for coastal erosion control and offshore engineering constructions along the Mediterranean and Red Sea coasts, especially Suez Canal coasts in Egypt were used in this study. Seam strength and its efficiency are an important parameter for geotextiles seam performance. Seam efficiency is the ratio of seam strength to fabric strength. Seam efficiency $\geq 90\%$ is more important for coastal erosion control application (according to the instructions of the Egyptian Coastal Protection Authority). Table 1 shows the physical and mechanical properties of this type of geotextiles fabric.

Table 1 - Physical and mechanical properties of nonwoven geotextiles

Test	Test Method	Result	Unit
1- Mass per unit area	EN ISO 9864	512	g/m ²
2- Thickness @ 2 kpa	EN ISO 9863-1	3.38	mm
3- Wide width tensile strength	MD	40.5	kN/m
	MCD	47.8	
4- Elongation @ max. load	MD	70	%
	MCD	65	
5- CBR puncture resistance	EN ISO 12236	6.12	kN
6- Equivalent Opining Size	EN ISO 12956	< 74	mμ (micron)
7- Raw material	100% polypropylene(include 15% low melt flbers)		

2.2. Sewing yarns

In this study, 12x3, 15x3 and 18x3 Tex filament polyester yarns were used. The fineness of the filament polyester fibers used was 1.2 Denier. Table 2 shows the physical and mechanical properties of the sewing yarns were used.

2.3. Stitch and seam type

In this study, 101 and 401 stitch with prayer type was used. The following diagrams (figure 1) indicate the prayer seam type with 1, 2 and 3 sewing lines. The other types of seams ("J" and "butterfly" seams) are more difficult to produce there for to increase the thickness when bending during the sewing process.

Table 2 - Physical and mechanical properties of the sewing yarns were used

Test	Test Method	Result			Unit
		-1	0	+1	
1- Yarn count		12x3	15x3	18x3	Tex
2- Twist in Yarns	ASTM D 1423	750	730	720	T/m
3- Tensile strength	ASTM D 2256	37	34.7	34.5	g/denier
4- Elongation @ max. load		28	25	23	%

Figure 3 - Prayer seam type

2.4 Sewing machine

Figure 4 - The yarn path of the field sewn machine

The equipment selected must be capable of producing a specific stitch geometry with the correct yarn type, denier, and should be selected based on the type of installation, geotextile construction and absolute seam strength requirements. There are two types of sewing equipment most commonly used: a) single-needle hand-held sewing machines and b) double-needle sewing machines, usually table mounted. Both methods are available in the field and in the factory. (1)

2.5. The Experimental parameters

The three factors sewing yarn count, number of sewing lines and type of stitch have been chosen for this factorial design experiment each with three levels except stitch type with only two levels. Coded levels with their respective values for the process parameters are shown in table 3.

Table 3 - The Experimental parameters and their levels

Parameters	Notation	Levels		
		-1	0	+1
Sewing yarn count (tex)	X ₁	12x3	15x3	18x3
Number of sewing lines	X ₂	1	2	3
Stitch type	X ₃	101	-	401

The ASANO tensile machine was used to measure the tensile strength of geotextiles and seams. The readings were recorded for each of the identified tests.

2.6. Response Surface Methodology (RSM) method

In this study, Response Surface Methodology (RSM) with Factorial design was used. Response Surface is affected by a number of variables and the aim is to optimize this response. Response Surface is a set of mathematical and statistical approaches that are useful for modeling and problem analysis. The process of sewing nonwoven geotextiles is influenced by several input factors that consistently results in a set of output responses. The best method to explore the relationship between the input and output is the response surface methodology since it can determine the exact value within any given range of parameters value. The best technique to investigate the relationship between input and output is to use the response surface approach, which can identify the precise value within any given range of parameter values. The factorial design, which presented in 1960, is considered to be the most practical RSM design in this case. This design is more effective with small number of runs. The factorial design (3²x2) has been used to calculate optimal result and also to find significance of each factor through *STATISTICA version 10* software computes variance. Through software computes variance, the factorial design has been utilized to identify significance of each factor and also to evaluation optimal results. Furthermore, the interaction between variables was analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA).

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Effect of sewing yarn count, number of sewing lines and type of stitch on geotextile sewing strength

Table 4 shows the design experiment and seam strength values (ST). Table 5 shows the result of analysis of variance (ANOVA) and parameters F value, p value, R², and adequate precision were used to check the model adequacies. As shown in Table 5, a p value less than 0.05 indicates that the corresponding model terms are significant, including X₁, X₂, X₃, X₁X₃, X₂X₃ and X₁X₂X₃. Furthermore, it is shown that R² value of the model is 0.9150 which is good to 1. This means that only 91.50% of the whole variance data can be described by the model, and only 8.50% of the total variation cannot be explained, which indicates better accuracy. The quadratic model derived from the regression analysis of the experimental data is given below:

$$ST = 29.36 + 11.81 X_1 + 5.66 X_2 + 3.74 X_3 + 0.544 X_1 X_2 - 2.7 X_1 X_3 + 1.88 X_2 X_3 - 1.733 X_1 X_2 X_3$$

Where: X₁, X₂ and X₃ are sewing yarn count, number of sewing lines and stitch type respectively.

Equation 1 shows that the ST value is directly proportional to the increase in the concentration of sewing yarn count (X₁) number of sewing lines (X₂), stitch type (X₂), sewing yarn count and number of sewing lines interaction (X₁ X₂), and number of sewing lines and stitch type (X₂ X₃), corresponding to a positive constant value. Meanwhile, interaction between the sewing yarn count and stitch type (X₁ X₃) and sewing yarn count, number of sewing lines and stitch type, interaction (X₁ X₂ X₃) gave a negative effect on the ST value. Figure 1 shows the predicted against actual values for ST. The data distribution is relatively close to the straight line indicating that the regression model can predict the ST value. Furthermore, it is shown that R² value of the model is 0.9465 which is close to 1. This means that only 94.65% of the whole variance data can be described by the model, and only 5.35% of the total variation cannot be explained, which indicates greater accuracy. Figures 3a-d shows the variable interaction of the 3D surface and contour plots on seam strength response.

Table 4 - The Design Experiment and seam strength values

Run	Sewing yarn Count (tex) X ₁	No. of sewing line X ₂	Stitch Type X ₃	Sewing strength ST kN/m	Seam strength efficiency %
1	-1	-1	-1	14.8	30.96
2	0	-1	-1	18.11	37.89
3	1	-1	-1	36.38	76.11
4	-1	0	-1	10.12	21.17
5	0	0	-1	14.16	29.62
6	1	0	-1	45.1	94.35
7	-1	1	-1	13.95	29.18
8	0	1	-1	33.35	69.77
9	1	1	-1	44.65	93.41
10	-1	-1	1	16.24	33.97
11	0	-1	1	17.89	37.43
12	1	-1	1	35.23	73.70
13	-1	0	1	24.13	50.48
14	0	0	1	36.14	76.61
15	1	0	1	45.39	94.96
16	-1	1	1	32.13	67.22
17	0	1	1	44.43	92.95
18	1	1	1	46.36	96.99

Table 5 - The results of analysis of variance (ANOVA)

	sum of squares	DF	mean square	F-test	P-value
model	7407.2	7	1058.2	33.78486	4.45E-16
Sewing yarn Count X1	5132	1	5132	928.3	1.34524E-16
No. of sewing line X2	1192	1	1192	215.7	2.2745E-05*
Stitch Type X3	756	1	756	273.5	1.1782E-07*
X1*X2	238	1	238	21.6	0.063592
X1*X3	350	1	350	63.3	0.005285*
X2*X3	495	1	495	89.6	0.004925*
X1*X2*X3	586	1	586	53	0.045455**
R Square	0.9150				

*Significance level: $P \leq 0.01$ at 99%.

** Significance level: $P \leq 0.05$ at 95%

Figure 2 - The plot of predicted against to actual value for seaming strength

(A)

(B)

(C)

(D)

Figure 3 - a-d Surface and contour plots on seam strength response

The dark red-red compositions are desirable, while the green-yellow compositions are less desirable. Figures 3a and b displays the effect of sewing yarn count and number of sewing lines on seaming strength for stitch type 101. It is clear from the contour plot that with the increase in sewing yarn count seaming strength also increases but seaming strength decreases with different levels of number of sewing lines with decrease sewing yarn count. This can be explained due to that chain 101 unravels easily. And therefore, the optimum results with chain 101 were obtained by 18x3 tex and sewing yarn count 3 lines. But it is not guaranteed because each stitch is dependent on the next.

From Table 6 it is shown that R² value of the model is 0.9044 which is good to 1. The meaning behind this is that 90.44% variation can be explained by this model and only 9.56% of total variation cannot be described, which is an indication of well correctness.

Table 6 - Response surface equations, correlation coefficients and significant values for parameter affected on each stitch type 101 and 401 samples

Stitch type	Response surface equations	R ²	P-value				
			X ₁	X ₂	X ₁ X ₁	X ₁ X ₂	X ₂ X ₂
101	$Y_{101} = 19.37 + 14.54X_1 + 3.77X_2 + 5.62X_1X_1 + 2.27 X_1X_2 + 3.75 X_2X_2$	0.9044	1.39E-11*	0.002*	0.008*	0.1083	0.0646
401	$Y_{401} = 37.82 + 9.023X_1 + 7.54X_2 + 0.256X_1X_1 - 1.189X_1X_2 - 7.32X_2X_2$	0.9394	1.05E-08*	2.1E-07*	0.807	0.343	0.0003*

X₁: Sewing yarn Count, X₂: number of sewing lines

*Significance level: P ≤ 0.01 at 99%.

**Significance level: P ≤ 0.05 at 95%

Figures 3c and d displays the effect of sewing yarn count and number of sewing lines on seaming strength for stitch type 401. It is clear from the contour plot that with the increase in sewing yarn count and number of sewing lines seaming strength also increases. This can be explained due to the fact that as the sewing yarn count and number of sewing lines increase the binding force between the fibers of geotextiles increases by increasing the fiber to fiber-frictional coefficient that held the fiber more compactly at seaming zone and therefore causes seaming strength increases. And therefore, the optimum results with chain 401 were obtained by 18x3 or 15x3 tex sewing yarn count and number of sewing lines is 2 and 3 and give the seam strength that suits to the final application of geotextiles. Therefore, interaction between the 18x3 or 15x3 tex sewing yarn counts and 2 or 3 lines of sewing gave the best results for the seam strength with chain 401. In additional, that is suitable for the final application of geotextiles. From Table 6 it is shown that R² value of the model is 0.9394 which is close to 1. This means that 93.94% of the whole variance data can be described by the model, and only 6.06% of the total variation cannot be explained, which indicates good accuracy. Stitch 401 is formed by passing the loop of one sewing yarn through the loop of another sewing yarn. This type of stitch is more durable than back stitching and reduces the likelihood of puckering in the seam. But stitch type 101 is formed by passing the loop of one yarn through the loop of the same yarn. This type of stitch is very unsafe because each stitch is dependent on the next, and a single broken yarn could tear the entire stitch apart. Therefore, 401 stitches are significantly stronger and more durable than 101 stitches.

4. Conclusion

Seam strength and its efficiency are an important factor for seam performance of nonwoven geotextiles. The objective of this work was to study some factors affecting geotextiles seam strength which utilized for coastal erosion control and offshore engineering constructions by using surface response methodology. Factorial design of response surface methodology can be successfully used to analyze and optimize the parameters which influence seam strength of geotextiles properties. The seam strength and its efficiency properties of nonwoven geotextiles made from polypropylene fibers have been studied and analyzed. It is observed that the three factors sewing yarn count, number of sewing lines and two types of stitch parameters are significantly affected geotextiles seam strength and its efficiency. The experimental studies results carried out are summarized as follows:

- Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and parameters F-test, P-value, R^2 , and adequate accuracy were used to check the model suitability. They showed that the seam strength properties were significantly affected by sewing yarn count, number of sewing lines and two types of stitch parameters and its interactions (except interaction between sewing yarn count and number of sewing lines) at P-value ($P < 0.05$) for all samples.
- For stitch type 101, it is clear that with the increase in sewing yarn count seaming strength also increases but seam strength decreases with different levels of sewing lines number with decrease sewing yarn count. The optimum results with chain 101 were obtained by 18x3 tex and sewing yarn count 3 lines.
- For stitch type 401, it is clear that with the increase in sewing yarn count and number of sewing lines seaming strength also increases. The optimum results with chain 401 were obtained by interaction between the 18x3 tex sewing yarn counts and 2 lines of sewing lines or 15x3 tex with 3 lines of sewing lines gave the best results for the seam strength with chain 401. In addition, that is suitable for the final application of nonwoven geotextiles.

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